

A Time Series Forecast Model

Based on the Most Similar Pattern

Irina Chuchueva

Independent Energy Quantitative Researcher & Developer

`chuchueva@gmail.com`

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Abstract

This paper presents an English translation of a study originally published in Russian in 2010 in *Informational Technologies* (ISSN: 1684-6400, No. 12, pp. 43–47). The text has been adapted for an international audience.

The study introduces a time series forecasting model based on the most similar pattern (FMMSP). The model formulation is described together with a calibration procedure. The performance of the proposed approach is evaluated using time series of electricity consumption and electricity prices. ¹

Introduction

Forecasting future values of a time series based on its current and past observations is a fundamental problem in economics, trade, production planning, inventory control, and in-

¹The Python example of the FMMSP implementation could be found at <https://www.kaggle.com/code/irinachuchueva/forecast-model-on-the-most-similar-pattern>

dustrial process optimisation [1]. Forecasting methods continue to develop rapidly alongside advances in data storage and computational capabilities.

Forecasting approaches can be divided into intuitive and formalised methods [2]. According to [3], formalised methods are further classified into statistical methods and artificial intelligence methods. Statistical methods derive forecasts from mathematical relationships identified in historical data, reflecting dependencies between future and past values and, in some cases, external variables. Artificial intelligence methods attempt to emulate human reasoning when analysing historical data and generating forecasts. This study focuses on a statistical forecasting approach.

The mathematical relationship describing the dependence of future time series values on observed data is often referred to as an extrapolation model [4]. In this paper, the term *forecast* is used consistently. A new FMMSF is proposed.

The effectiveness of the proposed model is evaluated using time series of day-ahead electricity prices and electricity consumption. Forecasts of these quantities are required by system operators to manage both technical and economic aspects of power systems. They are also essential for market participants seeking to improve financial performance [3, 5, 6, 7].

Forecasting day-ahead prices in Russia presents specific challenges. As the electricity market has undergone reform, the pricing algorithm has changed over time. Prior to January 1, 2008, day-ahead prices were calculated using a different methodology. This evolving structure increases the complexity of forecasting and highlights its importance for market participants.

Although numerous models for forecasting electricity consumption have been developed [8, 9, 10], research in this area remains ongoing.

This paper is structured as follows. Section 1 describes the proposed model. Section 2 presents the calibration procedure. Section 3 reports empirical results, and the conclusion summarises the main findings.

1 Model Definition

This paper deals with discrete time series whose values are obtained at time instants $t_1, t_2, t_3, \dots, t_N$. Generally, these time instants may be unequally spaced.

Denote the time series $Z = z(t_1), z(t_2), z(t_3), \dots, z(t_N)$ as $Z_1^N = z_1, z_2, z_3, \dots, z_N$. A set of consecutive values $Z_t^M = z_t, z_{t+1}, z_{t+2}, \dots, z_{t+M-1}$ lying inside the time series Z_1^N is called the *pattern* of length M from this time series with start t ; $M \in [1, N - 1]$; $t \in [1, N - M]$. The time difference between the two patterns Z_t^M and Z_{t-k}^M is called the *lag* k , $k \in [1, t - 1]$.

The correlation coefficient of samples Z_t^M and Z_{t-k}^M is defined as

$$\rho_k = \frac{\text{cov}(Z_t^M, Z_{t-k}^M)}{\sqrt{D[Z_t^M]} \cdot \sqrt{D[Z_{t-k}^M]}}, \quad (1)$$

where $\text{cov}(Z_t^M, Z_{t-k}^M)$ is the covariance of the patterns, and $D[Z_t^M]$ and $D[Z_{t-k}^M]$ are their variances [1].

Based on the correlation coefficient (1), the author introduces a measure of *patterns' similarity*

$$\rho_k^M = \frac{|\text{cov}(Z_t^M, Z_{t-k}^M)|}{\sqrt{D[Z_t^M]} \cdot \sqrt{D[Z_{t-k}^M]}} \in [0, 1].$$

The value ρ_k^M depends on the length M of the patterns Z_t^M, Z_{t-k}^M , as well as on the lag k . The similarity measure ρ_k^M characterises the degree of linear dependence between the patterns Z_t^M and Z_{t-k}^M : the closer ρ_k^M is to one, the higher their linear dependence.

For a pattern Z_t^M , the author determines the values $\rho_1^M, \rho_2^M, \dots, \rho_{t-1}^M$ and finds their maximum value

$$\rho_{k_max}^M = \max(\rho_1^M, \rho_2^M, \dots, \rho_{t-1}^M).$$

The pattern corresponding to the lag k_max is denoted $Z_{t-k_max}^M$ and is called the **most similar pattern** to the original pattern Z_t^M . Thus, for the sample $Z_{t-k_max}^M$ the equalities

hold

$$\rho_{k_max}^M = \frac{|\text{cov}(Z_t^M, Z_{t-k_max}^M)|}{\sqrt{D[Z_t^M]} \cdot \sqrt{D[Z_{t-k_max}^M]}}$$

Similarity hypothesis If the samples Z_t^M and $Z_{t-k_max}^M$ have a value of $\rho_{k_max}^M$ close to one, then for some values of P , the samples Z_t^{M+P} and $Z_{t-k_max}^{M+P}$ will also have the value of $\rho_{k_max}^{M+P}$ close to one.

The forecasting results presented in Section 3 confirm the validity of the hypothesis for time series of electricity consumption and day-ahead prices. For time series from other subject areas, the validity of the hypothesis must be verified.

Let us switch to vector notation for pattern $\mathbf{Z}_t^M = (z_t, z_{t+1}, \dots, z_{t+M-1})^T$ and time series $\mathbf{Z}_1^N = (z_1, z_2, \dots, z_N)^T$.

Approximate the pattern \mathbf{Z}_t^M using the most similar pattern $\mathbf{Z}_{t-k_max}^M$:

$$\mathbf{Z}_t^M = a_1 \cdot \mathbf{Z}_{t-k_max}^M + a_0 + \mathbf{E}^M;$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{Z}}_t^M = a_1 \cdot \mathbf{Z}_{t-k_max}^M + a_0. \quad (2)$$

Here a_1 and a_0 are constants, \mathbf{E}^M is an M -dimensional vector of approximation errors, and $\hat{\mathbf{Z}}_t^M$ are the approximated values of the pattern \mathbf{Z}_t^M . Consequently, the pattern \mathbf{Z}_{N+1}^P can be expressed through some pattern \mathbf{Z}_τ^P lying inside the original time series \mathbf{Z}_1^N as follows

$$\mathbf{Z}_{N+1}^P = a_1 \cdot \mathbf{Z}_\tau^P + a_0. \quad (3)$$

The approach for determining the pattern \mathbf{Z}_τ^P is as follows.

- For the sample \mathbf{Z}_{N-M+1}^M , find the most similar pattern $\mathbf{Z}_{k_max*}^M$, where $k_max* = N - M + 1 - k_max$.

- According to (2), approximate the pattern \mathbf{Z}_{N-M+1}^M using the pattern $\mathbf{Z}_{k_max*}^M$:

$$\hat{\mathbf{Z}}_{N-M+1}^M = a_1 \cdot \mathbf{Z}_{k_max*}^M + a_0. \quad (4)$$

- In accordance with the similarity hypothesis, take the pattern $\mathbf{Z}_{\tau}^P = \mathbf{Z}_{t_max*+M}^P$ located on the time axis immediately after the most similar pattern (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Positions of samples $\mathbf{Z}_{k_max*}^M$, $\mathbf{Z}_{k_max*+M}^P$, \mathbf{Z}_{N-M+1}^M and \mathbf{Z}_{N+1}^P on the time axis

In formula (4), the constants a_1 and a_0 are determined by solving the least squares problem

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^M (\hat{z}_{N-M+1-i} - z_{N-M+1-i})^2 \rightarrow \min,$$

discussed in detail in [11].

Thus, the forecasted values $\hat{\mathbf{Z}}_{N+1}^P$ of the time series \mathbf{Z}_N are determined by the formula

$$\hat{\mathbf{Z}}_{N+1}^P = a_1 \cdot \mathbf{Z}_{k_max*+M}^P + a_0 = \text{FMMSp}(M), \quad (5)$$

which represents a time series forecast model based on the most similar pattern (FMMSp).

2 Model Calibration

The problem of identifying model (5), i.e., finding the parameter M , is solved as follows.

- Split the original time series Z_1^N chronologically into three parts in a 2:1:1 ratio. The resulting parts are called the *train* (50%), *valid* (25%), *control* (25%) periods of the time series, respectively.
- Determine the value of P , the forecast horizon, and the range of possible values of the parameter M . Initially, it is recommended to take a wide range of possible values of M , for example, $M \in [P, P \cdot 30]$, and later refine it sequentially.
- For each value of the parameter M from the established range, forecast the values of the time series within the train period.
- Based on the forecasting results, determine the mean absolute error (MAE)

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{i=1}^K |\hat{z}_i - z_i|, \quad (6)$$

where K is the number of time series values falling into the train period.

- Plot the dependence of MAE on M for the train period and determine the range of values of M corresponding to a stable minimum of MAE.
- An expert selects the model parameter M within the stable minimum range.
- Forecast values within valid period with a chosen M value. If results are satisfactory, the model is calibrated and its only parameter M is defined. If results are not satisfactory, an expert should perform forecasting using neighbouring values M within the stable minimum range.
- If no satisfactory value of M is found for the valid period, the FMMSP could be considered not efficient for a given time series.

An example of the dependence of MAE on M for the time series of electricity consumption of the European part of the Russian Federation is shown in Figure 2. Initially, the range $M \in [24, 360]$ was chosen within which the values $M \in [168, 240]$ were identified. At the final step, the value $M = 216$ was chosen by expert judgment.

Figure 2: Dependence of MAE on the model parameter M , $M \in [24, 360]$

3 Forecast Results

The following time series provided by JSC “ATS” [12] were used to test the effectiveness of the proposed model:

- electricity consumption of the European price zone (EZ);
- electricity consumption of the Siberian price zone (SZ);
- day-ahead price of the EZ;
- day-ahead price of the SZ.

Each time series contains hourly equally spaced values for the period from 01.09.2006 to 30.09.2009. In addition to forecasting hourly values of these time series for the next day, the task is to forecast aggregated daily values – total electricity consumption per day and the average day-ahead price per day. The parameters of the time series are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Parameters of Time Series

Resolution	Time Series	Length	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Hourly	Power consumption EZ (MWh)	27 023	81 441	10 640	57 847	110 586
	Power consumption SZ (MWh)	27 023	22 338	3023	15 328	30 666
	Day-ahead price EZ (RUB/MWh)	27 023	610	194	0	1559
	Day-ahead price SZ (RUB/MWh)	27 023	368	185	0	1029
Daily	Power consumption EZ (MWh)	1126	1 954 502	218 255	1 519 197	2 438 008
	Power consumption SZ (MWh)	1126	536 101	68 930	408 408	695 606
	Day-ahead price EZ (RUB/MWh)	1126	610	144	221	1204
	Day-ahead price SZ (RUB/MWh)	1126	368	176	0	734

The problem of forecasting time series of day-ahead prices and electricity consumption with hourly resolution consists of finding 24 hourly values of the time series for the next day. For series with daily resolution, the forecast problem consists of finding one value for the next day. According to [3], both forecast problems fall into the category of short-term forecasting.

The period from 01.03.2009 to 30.09.2009 (seven months, about 5000 values for time series with hourly resolution; about 200 values for series with daily resolution) was used as the *control period* for forecasting.

Tables 2 and 3 present numerical results of forecasting accuracy, as well as the model parameters M for each time series obtained by solving the identification problem according to the scheme in Section 2. The given values of the parameter M can be used as a basis when working with time series of electricity consumption and day-ahead prices. For time series from other subject areas, the identification problem must be solved ab initio.

To estimate the forecast accuracy, in addition to the MAE value, the mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) was also evaluated

$$\text{MAPE} = \frac{1}{Q} \sum_{i=1}^Q \frac{|\hat{z}_i - z_i|}{z_i} \cdot 100\%,$$

where Q is the number of time series values falling into the control period.

3.1 Electricity Consumption Forecast Results

The results of forecasting electricity consumption for control period are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Electricity Consumption Forecast Accuracy

Time Series	Resolution	M	MAE, MWh	MAPE, %	Calc. Time, hr
Power consumption European price zone	Hourly	216	1347	1.04	1.80
	Daily	6	19 736	1.10	0.15
Power consumption Siberian price zone	Hourly	24	378	1.86	4.20
	Daily	8	7727	1.44	0.05

The obtained MAPE values for short-term forecasting lie in the range from 1.04% to 1.86%.

Let us compare the achieved accuracy with the forecast accuracy of electricity consumption reported in other publications. [3] describes the results of short-term forecasting of electricity consumption of the Shanghai Power Grid and reports MAPE values of various forecast models ranging from 2.8% to 3.4% depending on their features. The developers of the specialised software package “Energostat” in [7] report MAPE values for short-term forecasting of electricity consumption for regions of the Russian Federation for the year 2000, which lie in the range from 1.21% to 3.32% (depending on the region). The Austrian company iRM, producer of the iOPT PRO software for electricity consumption forecasting, indicates MAPE values for short-term electricity consumption forecasting of 1–2%.

The presented results of short-term electricity consumption forecast reveal the effectiveness of utilising the time series FMMSF to solve the problem of forecasting electricity consumption time series.

3.2 Day-Ahead Prices Forecast Results

The results of forecasting day-ahead prices accuracy are presented in Table 3.

From the table it can be seen that the MAPE values for day-ahead prices of the Siberian price zone are high due to the fact that in the control period there are zero values of day-ahead prices, which were replaced by 0.01 (i.e., 1 kopek/MWh) during error analysis.

Table 3: Day-Ahead Prices Forecast Accuracy

Time Series	Resolution	M	MAE, RUB/MWh	MAPE, %	Calc. Time, hr
Day-ahead price	Hourly	360	49.54	7.00	2.10
European price zone	Daily	16	34.50	4.81	0.15
Day-ahead price	Hourly	84	65.90	39.78	4.93
Siberian price zone	Daily	30	60.39	32.93	0.04

The task of forecasting day-ahead prices for Russia is new, so it is not possible to perform a comparison with other studies. For a similar problem of forecasting energy market prices in Spain and California, [5] reports MAPE values of 5–10% (depending on the month). Furthermore, [5] states that this level of forecasting accuracy is sufficient for effective financial planning in these markets. The forecast model proposed in the present study made it possible to obtain MAPE values of 4.8% and 7.0% for the European price zone. On this basis, it can be argued that the developed forecast model is effective for short-term forecasting of day-ahead prices in the European price zone. At the same time, Table 3 shows that the problem of forecasting day-ahead prices for the Siberian price zone requires additional research and model refinement.

Conclusion

The paper proposes a time series FMMSP. The main features of the proposed model are as follows.

- The FMMSP solves short-term forecasting problems (from 1 to 50 time steps ahead).
- The model does not impose restrictions on the stationarity of the time series.
- To work with the model it is recommended that the time series contains at least 1000 observations.
- The model can be extended to solve the problem of time series forecasting taking into account the influence of independent variables represented as other time series (for

example, taking temperature into account when forecasting electricity consumption).

The results presented in the paper confirm the effectiveness of utilising the model for forecasting day-ahead prices and electricity consumption time series. Future work will evaluate the effectiveness of the model for forecasting time series from other subject areas.

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